

REVIEW ON SATURATED FAT AND UNSATURATED FAT AND HEALTH IMPACT ON HUMAN

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Abstract: The impact of dietary fats on human health has been extensively studied, with recent evidence emphasizing the importance of the quality of lipids in shaping cardio-metabolic health. While long-chain saturated fatty acids (LCSFA) may negatively affect metabolic health, short- and medium-chain saturated fatty acids (SCSFA and MCSFA) exhibit beneficial or neutral effects. Substituting saturated fats with monounsaturated (MUFA) and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) has been associated with improved blood lipids and glycemic control. Saturated fats, solid at room temperature and primarily found in animal products, show varying health effects based on their food source. In contrast, unsaturated fatty acids (UFAs), essential components with therapeutic value, contribute to preventing oxidative stress, inflammation, and various diseases. Molecular structures of saturated and unsaturated fats play crucial roles in functionality, health impact, and potential applications in food sciences. Limiting saturated fat intake is recommended to mitigate risks of colorectal cancer, mitochondrial dysfunction, and cardiometabolic diseases, with the incorporation of unsaturated fats offering health benefits and reducing the risk of chronic diseases. Further research is needed to validate these findings and provide comprehensive dietary recommendations.

Keywords: Saturated fat, health problem, Unsaturated fat, high pressure Introduction

Saturated fat and unsaturated fat have been extensively studied for their impact on human health. Existing reviews have limitations, such as a lack of focus on people-important outcomes and a substantial risk of bias issues. However, recent evidence suggests that the quality of dietary lipids, rather than just their energy density, plays a crucial role in shaping cardio-metabolic health [1]. Long-chain saturated fatty acids (LCSFA) have been shown to negatively affect metabolic health, while short- and medium-chain saturated fatty acids (SCSFA and MCSFA) may have beneficial or neutral effects. Substituting saturated fats with monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) has been associated with improved blood lipids and markers of glycemic control [2].

Figure 1. Saturated and unsaturated fatty acid structure.

It is reasonable to recommend replacing saturated fats with unsaturated fats and avoiding the consumption of industrial trans-fats. Further research is needed to validate these findings and provide more comprehensive recommendations.

Objectives

To identify the chemical composition and the structure of fats to take measures to balance the nutrition.

Discussions

Saturated fat

Saturated fat in food refers to a type of fat that is solid at room temperature and is primarily found in animal products such as meat and dairy. It has been found that the effects of saturated fat on health can vary depending on its food source. Dairy-saturated fat has been associated with lower cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk, while meat-saturated fat is linked to a higher CVD risk. In China, the intake of total saturated fatty acids (SFAs) and even-chain SFAs was associated with higher total mortality in women, while odd-chain SFAs were associated with lower total mortality in both men and women [3]. The association between the consumption of SFAs from different food sources and overall diet quality remains uncertain, but intake of SFAs from low nutritive value foods is inversely associated with overall diet quality. The impact of saturated fat intake on health differs across food groups and even between foods within the same food group, such as dairy [4].

Unsaturated fat

Unsaturated fatty acids (UFAs) are bioactive compounds found in natural edible resources. They have various uses and biological activities, including therapeutic value in preventing oxidative stress, inflammation, cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases, cancer, and osteoporosis [5]. UFAs, such as omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids, are essential membrane components and play a central role in the proper functioning of the nervous system, cardiovascular system, and anti-atherogenic properties. UFAs can be found in foods of animal origin, but their determination can be challenging due to the presence of impurities and assay conditions [6]. The addition of UFAs to milk-containing

food products can prevent off-flavour that occurs over time. The use of unsaturated oils without the addition of trans fats has been investigated to provide similar functional properties to food products as saturated and trans fats [7].

Difference between saturated and unsaturated fats

Saturated fats and unsaturated fats have different effects on various aspects of health. Saturated fatty acids (SFAs) can lead to mitochondrial dysfunction and metabolic disorders, while unsaturated fatty acids (UFAs) counterbalance these effects. UFAs have therapeutic value in preventing oxidative stress, inflammation, cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases, cancer, and osteoporosis [8].

Figure 2. Classification of saturated and unsaturated fats

In terms of amyloid aggregation, unsaturated phospholipids catalyze the formation of more toxic amyloid aggregates compared to saturated lipids [9]. When it comes to the dopamine system, a diet high in saturated fat affects dopamine release and uptake in the nucleus accumbent, while a diet high in unsaturated fat preserves normal metabolic and behavioural parameters as well as dopamine signalling. In the context of fear learning and memory, saturated fatty acids, particularly myristic and palmitic acids, play a role in memory acquisition [10].

Molecular Structure of Saturated Fats

The molecular structure of saturated fat in food plays a significant role in its functionality and impact on health. Consumption of saturated fat has been shown to increase cholesterol levels in humans [7]. However, saturated fats are important for the physical properties of many food products [3,5]. The structure of saturated fat can be characterized by its chain length and the number and position of carbon-carbon double bonds [11]. Determining the precise structural properties of saturated fat is challenging, but new analytical methods using liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry have been developed to identify the

position of double bonds in fatty acid molecules [12]. Understanding the molecular structure of saturated fat is crucial for designing fat replacers and functional food materials that mimic the performance of saturated fat during food manufacturing operations [13]. Additionally, knowledge of the molecular structure of saturated fat can help in the development of personalized food colloids for individuals with specific dietary needs or digestive disorders.

Molecular Structure of Unsaturated fats

Unsaturated fats in food have different molecular structures that can affect their properties and functions. The position and number of carbon-carbon double bonds in fatty acids (FAs) play a crucial role in determining their physiological characteristics [14]. Analytical methods such as liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) coupled with solvent plasmation can be used to determine the double bond position of mono- and poly-unsaturated FAs [15]. Electrospray ionisation Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry (ESI FT-ICR MS) can be employed to characterize the molecular composition of free fatty acids (FFAs) and triacylglycerols (TAGs) in various vegetable oils [16]. Charge-switch derivatization reagents and charge-remote fragmentation pathways can be used to separate and identify FA isomers in biological samples, enabling the assignment of position(s) of unsaturation and the structure of the FA [17]. Understanding the molecular structure of unsaturated fats in food is important for their characterization, analysis, and potential applications in food, health, and medical sciences [18].

Consumption of Saturated Fats in the Diet

Limiting saturated fats in your diet is recommended for several reasons. High intake of saturated fatty acids (SFAs) has been associated with a higher risk of colorectal cancer (CRC) [9,11]. Additionally, excessive dietary uptake of SFAs can cause mitochondrial dysfunction and metabolic disorders [5]. Circulating total SFAs are positively associated with an increasing risk of cardiometabolic diseases, including cardiovascular disease (CVD), coronary heart disease (CHD), and stroke [3]. On the other hand, reducing SFA intake and incorporating unsaturated fatty acids (UFAs) into the diet can help counterbalance these detrimental effects and reduce the risk of chronic diseases [19]. Furthermore, replacing SFAs with polyunsaturated fats has been shown to have favourable effects on intrahepatic lipid content (IHL) and postprandial glycemia, leading to a reduction in liver fat content. Overall, limiting saturated fats in your diet can help improve health outcomes and reduce the risk of various chronic diseases [13,20-24].

Conclusion

The nuanced relationship between saturated and unsaturated fats underscores the importance of dietary lipid quality in shaping human health. While long-chain saturated fatty acids may have adverse metabolic effects, short- and medium-chain variants exhibit potential benefits. Substituting saturated fats with monounsaturated and polyunsaturated counterparts shows promise for improving blood lipids and glycemic control. The impact of

saturated fats on health varies across food sources, emphasizing the need for a nuanced approach. The molecular structures of these fats are critical for functionality and potential applications in personalized nutrition. Limiting saturated fat intake is advised to mitigate risks of colorectal cancer, mitochondrial dysfunction, and cardiometabolic diseases, with the incorporation of unsaturated fats offering protective effects. The complex interplay between lipid types necessitates ongoing research for comprehensive dietary recommendations to promote optimal health outcomes.

REFERENCE

1. Johnston, B. C., Zeraatkar, D., Steen, J., de Jauregui, D. R. F., Zhu, H., Sun, M., & Bala, M. M. (2023). Saturated fat and human health: a protocol for a methodologically innovative systematic review and meta-analysis to inform public health nutrition guidelines. *Systematic Reviews*, 12(1), 1-8.
2. Dissanayake, K., Rifky, M., Jesfar, M., Makhmayorov, J., Rakhimkulov, S., & Abdullayev, B. (2023, November). Technology Development to Measure Chemical and Oxidative Stability of Edible Oils Using Fourier Transform-Infrared Spectroscopy. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1275, No. 1, p. 012007).
3. Bordoni, L., Zec, M., Naumovski, N., & Sergi, D. (2023). The role of dietary fatty acids in metabolic health. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 14, 1211151.
4. Dissanayake, K., Rifky, M., Jesfar, M., Makhmayorov, J., Rakhimkulov, S., Abdullayev, B., & Samadiy, M. (2023, November). Development of Technology to Incorporate Curry Leaves (*Murraya Koenjii*) to Develop Functional Chicken Sausage and Evaluation of Chemical Properties. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1275, No. 1, p. 012008).
5. Rifky, M., Serkaev, K., & Samadiy, M. (2023). Technology Development to Incorporate Functional Oil Sources in Yoghurt to Improve Functional Properties. *Journal of Coastal Life Medicine*, 11, 928-938.
6. Ataxodjayeva, I. D., Akramova, R. R., Rifky, M., & Dissanayake, K. (2023). Study of mineral substances in easily digestible rabbit meat. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 90-93).
7. Wu, T., Liu, R., Zhang, L., Rifky, M., Sui, W., Zhu, Q., ... & Zhang, M. (2022). Dietary Intervention on Depression-A review. *Food & Function*, 13, 12475-12486
8. Rifky, M., Jesfar, M., Dissanayake, K., Ermat, S., & Samadiy, M. (2024). Development and evaluation of an automated irrigation system for ordinary agriculture farms. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 480, p. 03013).
9. Wambogo, E. A., Ansai, N., Terry, A., Fryar, C., & Ogden, C. (2023). Dairy, Meat, Seafood, and Plant Sources of Saturated Fat: United States, Ages Two Years and Over, 2017–2020. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 153(9), 2689-2698.
10. Rifky, M., Jesfar, M., Dissanayake, K., Orif, U., & Samadiy, M. (2024). Production of yoghurts with the addition of microencapsulated cinnamon, garlic and cumin oil with corn oil. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 480, p. 03014).
11. Zhuang, P., Cheng, L., Wang, J., Zhang, Y., & Jiao, J. (2019). Saturated fatty acid intake is associated with total mortality in a nationwide cohort study. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 149(1), 68-77.
12. Dissanayake, KDKK., Rifky, ALM., Nurmukhamedov, K. S., & Samadiy, M. A., The diverse function of sodium chloride in meat products in meat processing., Current problems of creating and using high technologies for processing mineral resources in Uzbekistan (2023).
13. Johnston, B. C., Zeraatkar, D., Steen, J., de Jauregui, D. R. F., Zhu, H., Sun, M., ... & Bala, M. M. (2023). Saturated fat and human health: a protocol for a methodologically

innovative systematic review and meta-analysis to inform public health nutrition guidelines. *Systematic Reviews*, 12(1), 1-8.

14. Kumara, K., Rifky, M., & Samadiy, M. (2023). Application and regulation of nitrate and nitrite in manufacturing of chicken sausage. *Theoretical and experimental chemistry and modern problems of chemical technology*, 1(01).

15. Harrison, S., Brassard, D., Lemieux, S., & Lamarche, B. (2020). Dietary saturated fats from different food sources show variable associations with the 2015 Healthy Eating Index in the Canadian population. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 150(12), 3288-3295.

16. Dissanayake, KDKK., Rifky, ALM., Nurmukhamedov, K. S., & Samadiy, M. A. The impact of sodium ascorbate in processed meat, Current problems of creating and using high technologies for processing mineral resources in Uzbekistan (2023) 54-55.

17. Chen, L., Zhang, Q., Meng, Y., Zhao, T., Mu, C., Fu, C., ... & Chen, Q. (2023). Saturated fatty acids increase LPI to reduce FUNDC1 dimerization and stability and mitochondrial function. *EMBO reports*, 24(4), e54731.

18. Dissanayake, KDKK., Rifky, ALM., Nurmukhamedov, K. S., & Samadiy, M. A. The impact of water holding capacity and CaCl₂ addition levels on processed meat quality, Current Problems of Creating and Using High Technologies for processing mineral Resources in Uzbekistan (2023) 66-67.

19. Liu, Y., Shen, N., Xin, H., Yu, L., Xu, Q., & Cui, Y. (2023). Unsaturated fatty acids in natural edible resources, a systematic review of classification, resources, biosynthesis, biological activities and application. *Food Bioscience*.

20. Dissanayake, KDKK., Rifky, ALM., Nurmukhamedov, K. S., & Samadiy, M. A. The impact of myoglobin levels on the colour of chicken sausage, The scientific and practical conference of the republic (2023) 424-427.

21. Zhao, Y., Liu, R., Qi, C., Li, W., Rifky, M., Zhang, M., ... & Sui, W. (2021). Mixing oil-based microencapsulation of garlic essential oil: impact of incorporating three commercial vegetable oils on the stability of emulsions. *Foods*, 10(7), 1637.

22. Liu, R., Ci, X., Liu, L., Wang, X., Rifky, M., Liu, R.,... & Zhang, M. (2024). Chitosan entrapping of sodium alginate/Lycium barbarum polysaccharide gels for the encapsulation, protection and delivery of *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* with enhanced viability. *Inter. Jour. of Biolo. Macromo.*, 129615.

23. Yki-Järvinen, H., Luukkonen, P. K., Hodson, L., & Moore, J. B. (2021). Dietary carbohydrates and fats in nonalcoholic fatty liver disease. *Nature Reviews Gastroenterology & hepatology*, 18(11), 770-786.

24. Parry, S. A., & Hodson, L. (2017). Influence of dietary macronutrients on liver fat accumulation and metabolism. *Journal of Investigative Medicine*, 65(8), 1102-1115.

25. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abduganievich, D. N., Nematovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). EFFECT OF FORCES ON AIR CONVEYING DEVICES AND NETWORK ON COTTON SEED QUALITY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 771-775.

26. Nematovich, S. S., Abduganievich, D. N., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCTION OF CERAMIC MATERIALS AND ITS VALUE TODAY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 768-770.

27. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abdug'aniyevich, D. N., Ne'matovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. M. (2021). Methods Of Kinematic Study of Flat Base Mechanisms. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3, 208-214.

28. Садир Нематович Шодиев¹, Неъматжон Садирович Шодиев². (2024). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЗАБИВАЕМОСТИ ТРУБОК РАДИАТОРА НА ТЕПЛОВОЕ СОСТОЯНИЯ ДВИГАТЕЛЯ. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 145–151. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/32>

29. Usarov, Jabbor E; Eshnaev, Nortoji J; Khakimov, Jamshid O; Saidova, Dilobar I; Ikrom Sh Inoyatov; и другие. *NeuroQuantology; Bornova Izmir Том 20, Изд. 16, (2022): 4614 -*

4622. DOI:10.48047/NQ.2022.20.16.NQ880468 <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/social-significance-creating-mechanism/docview/2816741596/se-2>
30. Shodiev, Z. O., Inoyatov, I. S., & Shodiev, N. S. (2020). NATURAL PASTE AND ITS VALUE TODAY. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 198-200).
31. J.Sh.Fazliev., Sh.M.Tojiev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>
32. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKLANLI EGATLARDAN G'O'ZANI SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>
33. Fazliyev, Z. S., Shokhimardonova, N. S., Sobirov, F. T., Ravshanov, U. K., & Baratov, S. S. (2014). Technology of the drip irrigation use in gardens and vineyards. The Way of Science, 56.
34. Ikrom, I. (2023). KASBIY TAYYORGARLIKNING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI BO'YICHA PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA-SINOV ISHLARI NATIJALARINING TAHLILI. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 626-633).
35. Shaxrilloevich, I. I. (2023). DIDACTIC CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF STUDENTS OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH. Academia Repository, 4(10), 142-145.
36. Саримсаков, М. М. (2023, May). СПОСОБЫ ПОЛИВА И УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ ИНТЕНСИВНЫХ ЯБЛОНЕВЫХ САДОВ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 14, pp. 173-175).
37. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Шохимарданова, Н. Ш. (2024). БОҒЛАРНИ ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШДА ТУПРОҚ-ГРУНТ НАМЛАНИШ КОНТУРИНИ АНИҚЛАШ УСЛУБИ. IMRAS, 7(2), 34-38.
38. Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). The Significance of Problem Situation Assignments in Teaching the Science of Machine Details. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 3(8), 30-32.
39. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR PROJECT-CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY. Экономика и социум, (10-2 (101)), 167-169.
40. AZ, S. Z. S. N. S. (2020). Analysis of the work on improving the design of dryers inside the ginning plants and the mode of drying.
41. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). KINEMATIC STUDY OF FLAT BASE MECHANISMS. E Conference Zone, 61–69. Retrieved from <https://www.econferencezone.org/index.php/ecz/article/view/888>
42. Shodiyev, Z. O., & Shodiyev, N. S. (2020). TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF THE MESH SURFACE ON THE SEED COTTON DURING THE SEPARATION OF COTTON FROM THE AIR STREAM. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 121-122).
43. Shodiyev, Z. O., & Shodiyev, N. S. (2020). KEY FACTORS FOR INCLUSION IN THE EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN IN THE CXM SEPARATOR AND THEIR IDENTIFICATION. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 119-121).
44. Sattorovich, S. U., & Qobil o'g'li, S. F. (2022). BUG 'DOY O 'SIMLIGI VA DONINING XALQ XO 'JALIGIDA BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI.
45. Khudaev, I. J., & Shoximardanova, N. S. (2023). FEATURES OF DRIP IRRIGATION OF CROPS. PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS, 2(24), 157-160.
46. Fazliyev, J. (2018). Modern irrigation methods for gardens. Science, 22, 24-26.